

KENAF (*hibiscus cannabinus* L.) GENETIC RESOURCES CONSERVED IN THE NATIONAL GENE BANK OF UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR UTILIZATION

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Abstract. *The article highlights the issues of kenaf genetic resources preserved in the National Gene Bank of Uzbekistan and their utilization. The kenaf collection in the gene bank consists of 373 accessions collected from 39 countries. More than 10 kenaf varieties have been created by breeders of Uzbekistan using this collection. The article presents the kenaf varieties recommended for cultivation in Uzbekistan, the number of accessions by country stored in the gene bank, as well as the analysis of accessions by reproduction year.*

Keywords: *kenaf, genetic resource, gene bank, collection, breeding, variety, reproduction, germination.*

Introduction: In the context of the world's growing population and climate change, the conservation and rational use of the genetic diversity of agricultural crops is of paramount importance. Genetic resources are an important source for creating new, productive, disease-resistant, and environmentally adapted crop varieties. The National Gene Bank of Uzbekistan conducts research aimed at preserving the genetic resources of crops important for the country's agriculture and using them on a scientific basis.

Kenaf, *Hibiscus cannabinus* L., is an annual herbaceous plant belonging to the mallow family (*Malvaceae* J.). Seed germination commences at temperatures of 10-12 °C, leading to the formation of viable seedlings at 13-15 °C. Vigorous seedling emergence is observed at temperatures between 20-22 °C. The optimal temperature range for kenaf growth and high yield formation lies between 23-25 °C. Heat requirements decrease towards the end of the growing season. Seed maturation can occur even at temperatures of 14-16 °C, coinciding with relatively dry air conditions.

Kenaf exhibits slow growth during the initial 30-45 days of its growth period, during which its root system undergoes significant development. Subsequently, above-ground biomass increases rapidly, growing at a rate of 6-10 cm per day. Stem elongation almost ceases with the emergence of narrow, lanceolate leaves. Protecting kenaf from weed infestation is crucial during the slow stem growth phase of early development. The flowering period of kenaf can last up to 6 weeks, with 1-2 flowers opening daily. Under Uzbekistan's conditions, secondary and tertiary flowers may also develop from leaf axils, resulting in the opening of 5-7 flowers per day. Kenaf is predominantly self-pollinating, with limited cross-pollination observed. Flowers typically open in the morning; cloudy weather may delay flower opening. Flowers remain open for a short period, wilting and closing in the afternoon. Due to the extended flowering period, boll and seed ripening is prolonged. Seed maturation occurs in the lower bolls while flowering continues in the upper parts of the stem. Technical maturity is reached in 110-130 days, whereas biological maturity (seed ripening) occurs in 130-150 days.

Kenaf exhibits stunted and weakened growth in environments with insufficient light. One of kenaf's agronomic advantages is its adaptability to a variety of soil types, including highly organic marshy soils and sandy desert soils. While it thrives best in neutral (pH) and fertile soils, kenaf can tolerate low soil fertility and a range of soil pH values, including alkaline and acidic conditions. Kenaf also demonstrates a high degree of tolerance to drought conditions.

Literature Review: Many studies are being conducted worldwide on the conservation and use of plant genetic resources. In this regard, the experience of scientific institutions such as the International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPK Gatersleben, Germany), the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI, Philippines), and the International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas (ICARDA, Syria) is noteworthy [1, 2, 3]. A number of works are also being carried out in Uzbekistan on the conservation and use of genetic resources [4, 5]. In particular, scientists from the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources have created genetic collections of cotton, cereals, vegetables, and other crops, and they are effectively used in the selection process.

Materials and Methods:

The study used 373 kenaf accessions stored in the National Gene Bank of Uzbekistan, as well as scientific reports and archival materials of the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources. The determination of quality indicators of plant seeds, monitoring was carried out according to the FAO methodology. Statistical and comparative methods were used in data analysis.

Results: The Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources conducts research on the collection of plant genetic resources, guaranteed storage for today's and future generations, the selection of primary sources for breeders as a result of its studies, and their effective use. The National Gene Bank, which is available at the Institute, stores more than 43,000 accessions of more than one hundred agricultural crops. The accessions have been collected over a century, and work is underway to enrich them. The National Gene Bank contains 373 live kenaf accessions collected from 39 countries from fiber crops.

More than 10 varieties have been created by the scientists of the Institute in different years using the kenaf collection, of which today the varieties Uzbekistan 1972, Uzbekistan 2142, Uzbekistan 2225, Uzbekistan 2268 (Table 1) are included in the list of varieties recommended for planting in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These varieties are distinguished from other varieties by their adaptation to local conditions, high yield, and high-quality fiber.

Also, accessions distinguished by valuable economic traits in field experiments by the scientists of the institute are given to breeders and bachelors, masters and doctoral students in higher educational institutions for their scientific experiments based on the application.

Table 1

Kenaf varieties recommended for planting in the territory of Uzbekistan

Variety name	*Original- order number	Year of registration	**Areas recommended for planting
Uzbekistan 1972	20	1984	11
Uzbekistan 2142	20	1990	11
Uzbekistan 2225	20	2004	11

Uzbekistan 2268	20	2010	11
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*Note: *20 - Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources (Uzbekistan Oil and Fiber Crops Research Station), ** - Tashkent region.*

The largest part of the varieties stored in the National Gene Bank comes from Russia (46 accessions), China (33 accessions), India (31 accessions), Uzbekistan (22 accessions), and Iran (21 accessions) (Table 2).

Samples from Armenia, Germany, Denmark, Algeria, France, United Kingdom, British Indian Ocean Territory, Iceland, Kyrgyzstan, South Korea, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, and Tajikistan were included in the study, with one sample representing each country.

Table 2

Number of accessions by country

Country name	Number of accessions	
	From one country	Total
Russia	46	46
China	33	33
India	31	31
Uzbekistan	22	22
Iran	21	21
Kazakhstan	17	17
Sudan	13	13
Indonesia	12	12
Cuba	11	11
Egypt	7	7
England, Mali, Tanzania	6	18
Africa, Australia, Italy, Romania, South Africa	5	25
Brazil, United States of America	4	8
Spain, Portugal, Ukraine	3	9
Hungary, Vietnam	2	4
Armenia, Germany, Denmark, Algeria, France, Great Britain, British Indian Ocean Territory, Iceland, Kyrgyzstan, South Korea, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Tajikistan	1	14
others	82	82
Total:		373

Accessions of agricultural crops are stored in the National Gene Bank in the medium-term gene bank. In order to maintain the germination rate of variety seeds, the germination rate of accessions in the gene bank is constantly monitored. Varieties with reduced seed germination are planted in the field, their reproduction is renewed, and they are returned to the gene bank. As a result of the renewal of reproduction over the years, today the oldest reproduction accessions belong to 2015, that is, 10-year-old seeds (Table 3).

Table 3

Renewal of accession reproduction by years, unit

№	Year	Number of accessions
1.	2015	2
2.	2016	2
3.	2017	52
4.	2018	55
5.	2019	78
6.	2020	100
7.	2021	34
8.	2022	50
Total:		373

Alongside the rejuvenation of the sample reproductions, the phenological phases and biometric characteristics of the plants were also investigated. Plant height in *Hibiscus cannabinus* L. is considered a crucial parameter that determines yield, product quality, and cultivation characteristics. It is directly influenced by the plant's genetic traits, cultivation conditions, and production goals. *Hibiscus cannabinus* L. exhibits intensive growth under optimal conditions, including a temperature of 25°C, sufficient soil nutrients, long daylight hours, and regular irrigation.

In 2024, field experiments revealed that the plant height of 58 kenaf collection samples, cultivated in the experimental field, ranged from 377 to 490 cm, with an average height of 440.6 cm.

Plant Height of Kenaf Collection Samples: Analysis of plant height, categorized into groups, revealed the absence of short-statured (1.5-2.0 m) and medium-statured (2.5-3.0 m) samples. All 58 examined samples were classified as tall-statured (greater than 3.5 m). This indicates that all the samples cultivated in the current year belonged to the tall-statured group.

Conclusion: The National Gene Bank of Uzbekistan has an important collection of kenaf genetic resources. The effective use of this collection will serve to develop kenaf breeding and seed production in Uzbekistan, and to create new, productive, and high-quality varieties. It is important to continue research on the conservation and use of genetic resources, enrich the collection with new accessions, and constantly monitor seed germination.

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